

NODES – Nord OvestDigitale e Sostenibile

Network of Teachers

SPOKE 4 – Digital and Sustainable Mountain

DELIVERABLE DN.N28

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Assessment of the experimental design of the outdoor education activities.

GREEN-Univda initiated a network for outdoor education in 2023, using Sensitive Dance as a tool to enhance children's connection with Nature. This research aims to test if Sensitive Dance, compared to physical education, increases children's biophilia, using psychometric scales. The study also explores the impact of outdoor education on children's performance, comparing schools inside and outside the Gran Paradiso National Park. Results showed no significant differences between these school groups, potentially due to the nature of the activities, suggesting a need for continuous engagement and better tools for teachers. The research emphasizes the importance of balancing indoor and outdoor education, addressing the negative effects of reduced Nature exposure on urbanized children. Furthermore, the program will develop networking opportunities and knowledge maps to support teachers in promoting outdoor learning.

A) Connection with Nature and Sensitive Dance

Creation of a network of teachers on outdoor education and learning.

Introduction

In 2023, the Groupe de Recherche en Education à l'Environnement et à la Nature de l'Université de la Vallée d'Aoste (GREEN-Univda) initiated a network of educators dedicated to outdoor education and learning in the regions of Piedmont and Valle d'Aosta. To operationalize this new network, GREEN-Univda developed a Sensitive Dance work program. We hypothesized that Sensitive Dance, primarily engaging the kinesthetic channel, can enhance a child's innate connection with Nature. The study compared the effects of Sensitive Dance lessons to physical education classes on children's connectedness to Nature, using psychometric scales to measure this connection. By examining the potential benefits of Sensitive Dance, this research seeks to contribute to understanding and promoting biophilia in children.

Methods

The primary objective of this research is to falsify the hypothesis that Sensitive Dance has no effect on children's biophilia. This hypothesis is based on the personal experiences and testimonies of numerous sensitive dancers, which often align with descriptions provided by those who have experienced deep ecology. The GREEN Univda selected three psychometric scales: the Connectedness to Nature Scale (CNS; Mayer & Frantz, 2004), the Dispositional Empathy with Nature (DEN; Tam, 2013), and the Children's Affective Attitude toward Nature (CAAN; Cheng & Moore, 2012). These scales measure the degree of individual connection with Nature, empathy towards Nature, and affective attitude towards Nature, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The activities carried out within deliverable 28 allowed us to interact with schools both inside and outside the Gran Paradiso National Park, enabling us to test the methodology we had set out to apply. Despite the significant differences in environmental context (schools inside the park and schools in urban areas), no significant differences emerged. This could be due to the fact that the activities were carried out in a spot manner, while discussions with the teachers focused on planning more continuous activities. It emerged that more tools for teachers in nature education would be necessary for both the teaching staff and the students. We discussed how to balance educational and training activities in the classroom with that outdoors.

Research Program Development

A reduced 'experiential stimulation in Nature' (Barbiero and Berto, 2016) could be the cause of several phenomena suffered by urbanized children, such as chronic fatigue, restlessness, insomnia, and also, difficulty relating, concentration problems, stress, anxiety, unfounded fears, even leading to disorders such as depression and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD): this is the result of an education divorced from the natural context (Louv, 2011).

Our research activity seeks to provide educators with refined tools to measure children's connection with Nature and to analyze changes in classroom interactions, educational achievements, and children's interactions with the natural world. By comparing two schools located within the Gran Paradiso National Park with four schools outside the park (as control groups), the project will evaluate the hypothesis that enhanced outdoor education leads to improved children's performance. Specifically, the research will formulate precise inquiries to investigate three distinct relational domains: children's connection to Nature, the impact of outdoor versus indoor learning, and the dynamics of classroom interactions. In addition, the project will establish networking platforms to enable teachers to share effective pedagogical strategies and to collaboratively develop comprehensive knowledge maps detailing the regional landscape, its ecological characteristics, and relevant outdoor learning activities.